

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF RESEARCH TRAINING OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, due to the fundamental changes in the socio-economic life of society, many changes are taking place in the education system, as well as in its content and teaching technology. At the same time, it is noted that at present the educational system is faced with the task of teaching the student to think, teaching the necessary ways of action to solve various problems that arise in front of him at any age, and the difference between research and design.

Keywords: research, learning, activity, activity, design, interest.

Currently, due to the root changes in the socio-economic life of society, many changes are taking place in the education system and its content and teaching technology.

Today's education system is faced with the task of teaching students to think, to teach them the necessary ways of action to solve various problems that arise at any age. The main goal of general secondary education at the national level is to promote the formation of a competent person who is ready to actively participate in the social, economic, socio-political life of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Currently, Research is characteristic not only of a small group of professional researchers, but also of a person who is actively involved in professional life, which has become the order of life of modern people in any field [1].

The concept of "research" is stated in the "Big Soviet encyclopedia" as "the process of acquiring new knowledge and is one of the types of cognitive activity." Cognitive activity is receptive (productive) for the learner.

The cognitive-modifying activity of the student is carried out using the so-called research method. A student with high intellectual and creative abilities should create conditions for independent learning, that is, create the opportunity for the student to independently organize and manage his activities.

The researcher-student is naturally inclined to study. Curiosity, an attempt to control, conducting experiments in one's own way is a process that accompanies a child's childhood. Research, search activity is a natural phenomenon inherent in the creation of a child.

The need to use the research method is explained by the student's interest and love for the environment in the process of obtaining knowledge. Independent research by a student has a great influence on finding answers to the questions that arise with the satisfaction of his personal requirements. In addition, independent research creates an opportunity for the development of

intellectual and creative abilities, thinking, research skills. The student can independently conduct research on the environment

In recent years, as a new term for the problem of "research activity", the term "research ethics", translated into Russian, has been introduced. The term "поведение" ("here" behavior") is often used in scientific and pedagogical literature and practice (culture of behavior, moral behavior, student behavior). And in our usage, the etymology of the word "morality" ("ethics") refers to the concept of "the totality of ethics, actions and actions of someone's life." In the pedagogical encyclopedia, "поведение" (here "behavior") is considered as "a reaction and action of a person, an animal, expressing its relationship with its environment." Human behavior refers to a system of conscious actions that are observed in the attitude of a person to his social environment. In the behavior of a person's personality, his character, temperament, requirements, views, tastes are traced. Emotion and sense play an important role in behavior or manners. And the main feature of research ethics is self-awareness.

The student's Ethics in the process of activity becomes his personal qualities. The properties of the personality, its ethics in general, public relations are considered as universal human values. At the same time, due to the fact that each person has a different relationship with his environment, his manners are also observed in different forms. The forms of human ethics are summarized in accordance with social relations and upbringing. A. I. Savenkov of research ethics, emphasizing that it is a complex mental phenomenon, says that it is not given a clear definition [3]. In one of his works, he explains as follows: research ethics considers the search for information, the sequence of actions directed from the unknown to the known. The author refers to "research ethics as an attempt to recognize the main object of mental demand in search activity, and research training is a type of training based on research ethics."

At the heart of research ethics is search activity, the student's desire to study the environment. At the head of the research ethic is its internal biological psychic natural requirement. At the heart of this claim is the Oriented Research reflex, identified by I. P. Pavlov. The reflex is a requirement that characterizes the mental response to the environment inherent in both humans and animals. Research ethics is considered as "observing the life activity of any living being." It serves as a development [4].

A person's research ethic is traced in creativity. Creativity is the main characteristic of research ethics. Research creative search has a two-way view of a person: the first is important in terms of obtaining some new product, the second is important in terms of the essence of the search process. A person is able to enjoy not only the result of his creativity, but also the creative, research process itself. Psychologists point to research ethics as important in the self-development of the individual.

Since 1999, research, research, and design activities of students have been created as a single system. And today this methodology is of particular need in the context of a competency-based approach to learning.

Project-translated from Latin *projectus* gives the concept of "preliminary". At the same time, the essence implies several concepts: a set of documents for certain buildings, a draft of some document, a certain plan.

The study is explained by the ability of a person to assimilate new knowledge as one of the types of cognitive activity in everyday use. If we focus on the features of scientific research in theoretical and practical terms.

Research learning is the main way of learning, built on the child's natural desire to independently learn about his environment. The main goal of research training is the formation of the student's readiness and ability to independently master new creative ways of activity in any area of human culture.

This is how research differs from design. The study does not involve the creation of a pre-planned object. It is the process of searching for the unknown, searching for new knowledge. This is one of the cognitive activities of a person.

Therefore, design and ResearchThe directions of the types of activities are different in essence and content.

Research design differs from research in that design is experience-oriented. The person

implementing the project solves not only the new, but also the real problem that he is facing.

Project development is usually a creative activity, but creativity depends on various external circumstances that go beyond the task of finding the truth. It should not be forgotten that a theoretical project can be performed using ready-made algorithms and drawings.

Although design has its limits on how to solve problems, it continues to deepen as much as research.

By evaluating research and design opportunities, you should be able to understand the benefits of learning design techniques and research methods while working with your child. In addition to design, research work can be carried out. It should be borne in mind that the study carried out by the method of methodological design involves drawing up a clear plan for making specific forecasts, checking their results according to the plan [5].

Research should be carried out freely, without restrictions on certain external conditions.

The main result expected at all stages of research work is the child's ability to creatively assimilate the newly acquired knowledge; the development of skills in processing the acquired material and research ethics. The result of his small study should not be confused with others.

The main result for the teacher is not a home layout or drawing of the child, but the most valuable creative research work, new knowledge and skills.

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